

A BIBLOMETRICS STUDY ON ELECTRONIC PHD THESES AND DISSERTATIONS OF THE FACULTY OF LAW IN INFLIBNET SHODHGANGA REPOSITORY

Dr. MOHAN JAMDADE

Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Pune. New Law College, Pune.

Dr. SACHIN S. SURYAWANSHI

Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Pune. Abhijit Kadam Insitute of Management & Social Sciences, Solapur.

SANJEEV H. CHAVAN

Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Pune. Yashwantrao Mohite Institute of Management Karad.

Abstract

The objective of this study is to examine the availability and legibility of Law Faculty PhD program theses uploaded on the Shodhganga repository. For this study, Data was retrieved from Shodhganga ETD Repository and Google Scholar. One hundred and forty nine Indian universities have deposited 3441 PhD theses in Shodhganga Repository till December 2021. Punjab University has uploaded the maximum number of PhD theses on Shodhganga and Kuvempu University has the maximum number of citations.

Keywords: Bibliometric, INFLIBNET, Institutional Repository, Law Research, Shodhganga.

INTRODUCTION

According to Merriam –Webster dictionary, “**A dissertation embodying results of original research and especially substantiating a specific view, especially one written by a candidate for an academic degree**”¹.

At present, Shodhganga digital repository is a prominent source of collecting literature references to be revealed in the bibliography to determine the originality of research. The PhD Theses of the faculty of Law submitted and uploaded to universities in India are given citations as an entry in the Bibliographic reference section to remark on intellectual right. A PhD thesis is an idea that is discussed and presented with evidence to show that it is authentic. The main sources of the work are: Information memory plays an important role Postgraduate education is required Sources of academic publications from universities²

Most academic publications Represented by academic papers and electronic papers (ETD), especially doctoral dissertations or dissertations containing: Results of individual studies for at least 3 years of scientific research done in the laboratory by research teams, laboratories, schools or companies. Created by the university as part of Academic Gray literature is considered this is library material. Manufactured in limited numbers with a specific law³

Shodhganga (India's Digital Electronics Store) thesis and dissertation is a centralized management Dissertation Management Repository⁴

It's an effort by Information and library network (INFLIBNET) to facilitate open access to Indian dissertations to the world academic community. Online Availability of electronic Theses through Shodhganga allows easy access and archiving of Indian theses and helps to increase the level and quality of research. There are several issues associated with the doctoral theses such as duplication, poor quality outcomes, authenticity and low visibility. Shodhganga as a repository help to overcome these issues by improving the visibility and search results.⁵

Presently, a total of 380968 full-text theses are available in this repository added by 568 universities out of 1057 who have contributed to this repository. A total of 654 Universities have signed MOUs for sharing or uploading the PhD theses on this repository⁵

As per notification by the University Grants Commission (UGC) (Minimum Standards and Procedure for Award of M.Phil. / Ph.D Degree, Regulation, 2009 Amendment made on 2016) dated May 5, 2016, it is required for university researchers to submit electronic versions of Theses and dissertations to facilitate open access to Indian Theses and dissertations to the academic community worldwide. Further, the online availability of electronic Thesis via centrally managed digital repositories are also helpful to facilitate access to and archiving of Indian doctoral Theses. At the same time, this will also help to raise the standard and quality of research. The Regulation specifies who is responsible for hosting, maintaining, and developing the Indian digital infrastructure⁵.

The present study focuses on a detailed analysis of obtaining ability discernibility influences and current trends in law PhD Theses. In this paper, the authors are trying to highlight the contribution made by the central, private, state and deemed universities from all over India, which are associated with INFLIBNET by signing MoUs for the promotion of research through sharing ETDs in accessible repositories.⁵

LITERATURE REVIEW

As discussed earlier, Shodhganga is a repository undertaken and administered by INFLIBNET, which has been providing a common platform and space to the universities across India for uploading and sharing PhD Theses and dissertations in electronic form. Earlier, North Eastern Hill University took an imitative in signing MoUs with Shodhganga by approximately 2100 contributions in the repository and stood first among all the Northern central universities. The central university of this part of the nation has preferred the English language for its Theses and dissertations⁶.

There are several other networks exist which forms a repository of the research publications in form of e-books, e-journals, e-database, etc. The networks such as INFLIBNET, DELNET KALIBET etc. are some of the library networks played an invaluable role in the process of content sharing via information networks. Usually, the libraries with decentralized rules & regulations and having a network have been providing a common platform for library personnel and libraries to get along to communicate and support by

enhancing and improving access to resources and information to satisfy the unlimited demands of the users⁷.

This study thoroughly examines the contribution of Shodhganga to law research in the forms of ETDs uploaded by Indian universities. The Law departments across the country have contributed by uploading 2856 ETDs. The contributions status as period-wise, state-wise and university-wise contribution has been analyzed along with MOUs as well⁸.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To highlight the visibility of the Law PhD theses uploaded on INFLIBNET Shodhganga with the help of citation data and other Bibliometric details.
- To present the contribution as University-wise and State-wise of Law PhD theses submitted to Shodhganga repository.
- To identify the most contributed research supervisors in submitted Law PhD theses and further, identification of top five PhD theses according to citation analysis.
- To identify the top five universities contributing on Shodhganga repository based on the submissions and total score of citations.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers have adopted a Bibliometric approach for receiving, analyzing and summarizing information on Law PhD Theses published on Shodhganga repository. Adoption and usage of the Bibliometric method is helpful for researchers in many ways by employing a quantitative approach for the evaluation, review and consistent monitoring of the published research. The use of Bibliometric method is further helpful to highlight the objectivity in research of any domain in a quantitative perspective.

In the present study, the data have been collected for the period 1966-2021 for published Law PhD theses on Shodhganga repository. A total of 3441 PhD Theses from 149 Universities and institutions are available on Shodhganga for the identified period. Further, the citation data have been captured from Google Scholar for the qualitative and quantitative analysis. The analysis of data has been done using the Microsoft Excel application package.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Period-wise publications of PhD Thesis and received Citation

Table 1 clearly indicates that a total of 3441 Law PhD Theses are submitted to the Shodhganga repository for the period from 1966 to Dec 2021. It can be seen from the Table 1 that there is a regular increase in the Law PhD theses on year-on-year basis. Further, highest numbers of PhD Theses were contributed during the period from 2016 - 2021 which are 1421 in number constituting 41.30% of the total submitted these. Similarly, the highest number of citations 76 (44.40%) were received during 2011-15, followed by 36 (21.05%) citations from 2016 -2020. Figure 1 shows the period wise

published Law PhD theses and cited theses which is a clear indication that a large number of Theses are not performing in terms of citations.

Table 1: Period-wise publications of PhD Thesis and received citations

Sr.no	Period	No of Publication	% of Publication	Individual Ph D Thesis cited	% of Citation
1	1966- 1970	05	0.14%	01	0.58%
2	1971-1975	05	0.14%	01	0.58%
3	1976-1980	11	0.32%	03	1.06%
4	1981-1985	28	0.81%	04	2.33%
5	1986-1990	61	1.77%	03	1.06%
6	1991-1995	79	2.30%	11	6.43%
7	1996-2000	72	2.09%	06	3.50%
8	2001-2005	166	4.82%	08	4.67%
9	2006-2010	521	15.14%	21	12.28%
10	2011-2015	927	26.94%	76	44.44%
11	2016-2020	1421	41.30%	36	21.05%
12	2021	145	4.21%	01	0.58%
	Total	3441	100%	171	100%

Figure 1: Period wise Law PhD Theses published and cited

State-wise universities contributing LAW PhD Thesis to Shodhganga

In this study, a total of 150 universities from 28 states of India have deposited 3441 Law PhD Theses in Shodhganga repository. Among these, Uttar Pradesh (16.41%) is the leading with highest number of submitted Law PhD Theses submitted followed by Punjab (11.74%) and Haryana (9.47%). However, Punjab (81) has submitted average number of Theses university- wise followed by Haryana (47) and Himachal Pradesh (40). Figure 2 shows the geographical distribution of Law PhD Theses submitted.

Table 2: Indian States-wise contribution of LAW PhD Thesis to Shodhganga

S. No	State	No of Universities	No of Thesis	Average no theses deposited	% out of 3441	Rank
1	Uttar Pradesh	24	565	24	16.41%	1
2	Punjab	5	404	81	11.74%	2
3	Haryana	7	326	47	9.47%	3
4	Rajasthan	21	269	13	7.81%	4
5	Maharashtra	12	258	22	7.49%	5
6	Karnataka	9	247	27	7.17%	6
7	Gujrat	8	238	30	6.91%	7
8	West Bengal	6	221	37	6.42%	8
9	Andhra Pradesh	6	151	25	4.38%	9
10	Odisha	7	126	18	3.66%	10
11	Assam	3	121	40	3.51%	11
12	Madhya Pradesh	9	106	12	3.08%	12
13	Delhi	7	93	13	2.7%	13
14	Himachal Pradesh	2	80	40	2.32%	14
15	Tamilnadu	3	65	22	1.88%	15
16	Jammu & Kashmir	3	39	20	1.13%	16
17	Uttarakhand	4	38	10	1.1%	17
18	Goa	1	18	18	0.52%	18
19	Telangana	2	16	8	0.46%	19
20	Chhattisgarh	2	13	6	0.37%	20
21	Puducherry	1	13	13	0.37%	21
22	Bihar	1	11	11	0.31%	22
23	Kerala	2	7	3	0.2%	23
24	Manipur	1	5	5	0.14%	24
25	Meghalaya	1	7	7	0.14%	25
26	Tripura	1	4	4	0.11%	26
27	Sikkim	1	2	2	0.05%	27
28	Jharkhand	1	1	1	0.02%	28
	Total	150	3441	586	99.87	

*(Note: Average Thesis deposited rounded off to two decimal places).

Figure 2: State-wise details of Law PhD dissertations

Top five universities contributing to Shodhganga by LAW faculty

The top five universities contributing to Shodhganga in terms of Law PhD Theses are shown in Table 3. It can be clearly seen that Panjab University, Chandigarh is contributing nearly 232 Law PhD Theses followed by Maharshi Dayanand University with 221 and Aligarh Muslim University with 145 PhD Theses. Out of 3441 Law PhD Theses submitted by 150 universities, 801 Theses (23.27%) have been contributed by these five universities, refer Table 3.

Table 3: Top five universities contributing to Shodhganga by LAW faculty

Sr.no	Name of the University	No of the PhD Thesis Contributed	% of Contribution	Rank
1	Panjab University	232	28.96%	1
2	Maharshi Dayanand University	221	27.59%	2
3	Aligarh Muslim University	145	18.10%	3
4	Gauhati University	110	13.73%	4
5	Maharaja Ganga Singh University	93	11.61%	5
	Total	801	100	

Top five Universities received Citations for PhD Thesis

As shown in the Table 4, Kuvempu university has highest citation score of 33 followed by DeenDayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University (23) and Maharshi Dayanand University (22).

Table 4: Top five Universities received Citations for Law PhD Theses

Sr. no	Name of the University	Total Score of Citation received by University	Rank
1	Kuvempu University	33	1
2	Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University	23	2
3	Maharshi Dayanand University	22	3
4	Gujarat University	12	4
5	Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University	10	5
6	Solapur University	10	5
	Total	110	

University types wise contribution to Shodhganga

There are various categories in the university and institutions such as central, state, private, deemed, ect. As shown in Figure 3, state universities have contributed 2853 Law PhD Theses which is 82.91% of the total submission into the Shodhganga repository. The Central Universities have submitted 252 (7.32%) whereas Private Universities submitted 228 (6.63%) Law PhD Theses. The Deemed Universities have contributed with 108 (3.13%) Law PhD Theses.

Law PhD Theses Submitted (1966-2021)

Figure 3: University type-wise submitted Law PhD Theses

Leading research guides in Law subject from selected universities

Prof. C P Sheoran from Maharshi Dayanand University is the leading research supervisor who has supervised more than 30 Law PhD Theses. Prof. Rajshekhar from Karnataka University supervised 22 whereas Prof. Tayal Vimlendu supervised 20. Figure 4 shows the top five research supervisors in the field of Law.

Figure 4: Leading research supervisor for Law PhD Theses

Cited/uncited Thesis

The citation count is an indication of the credibility of the research. More number of citations means by better quality of work reported. The number of citations received by the Law Theses submitted in Shodhganga was analyzed. This is very outrageous to report that a large number of Theses (3270) remained uncited. Only 171 (4.96%) Law PhD Theses have been cited out of which 119 have got one citation each whereas only 6 Law PhD Theses have got more than 05 citations. Table 5 is showing the distribution of the number of cited/uncited Law PhD Theses. Figure 5 is showing the trends of total citation score.

Table 5: Distribution of the number of cited/uncited Law PhD Theses

Sr.no	No of Citation	No of PhD Thesis	% of Citation per PhD Thesis	Total Citation Score	% of Total Citation Score
1	Cited by 0	3270	95.03%	00	0.0%
2	Cited By 1	119	3.42%	119	4.19%
3	Cited By 2	35	1.01%	70	26.81%
4	Cited By 3	08	0.23%	24	9.16%
5	Cited By 4	03	0.08%	12	4.58%
6	Cited By 5	03	0.08%	15	5.75%
7	Cited By 6	02	0.05%	12	4.58%
8	Cited By 10	01	0.02%	10	3.81%
	Total	3441	100%	262	100%

Figure 5: Total cited Law PhD Theses

Leading research scholars in Law subject getting citation for thesis

As seen from Table 6, research scholar Jaswal Parmjit Singh from Panjab University 10 has got the highest citation for his PhD Theses followed by Krushna Chandra Jena (06)

from Utkal university and Dhar Pannalal form University of Calcutta.

Table 6: Leading research scholars in Law subject getting citation for thesis

S. No.	Research Scholar	Affiliating University	Citations	Rank
1	Paramjit Singh Jaswal	Panjab University	10	1
2	Krushna Chandra Jena	Utkal University	06	2
3	Pannalal Dhar	University of Calcutta		
4	B M Suresh	National Law School of India University, Karnataka	05	3
5	Beauty Banday	University of Kashmir		
6	Samiksha Godara	Maharshi Dayanand University		
7	Lingappa Siddamma	Gulbarga University	04	4
8	Parimala Veluvali	Symbiosis International University		
9	C K Gopala Krishnan Nair	Jawaharlal Nehru University	03	5
10	Rekha S Chavan	Karnatak University		
11	Navpreet Kaur	Panjab University		
12	Baldevbhai Prabhudas Patel	Saurashtra University		
13	Ashok Bharatlal Bansod	Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University		
14	K D Haveripeth	Karnatak University		
15	S Krishnamurthy	University of Mysore		
16	Shubhendu Kumar Jain	Dayalbagh Educational Institute		
17	Amita Punj	University of Delhi		

Leading research Guide in Law subject getting citation for thesis

As seen from Table 7, Prof. Balram K Gupta from Panjab University has got 10 citations for Law PhDs supervised followed by Prof. C Rajashekhar (07) from Karnataka University and Prof. B N Sampath from Utkal University.

Table 7: Leading research Guide in Law subject getting citation for thesis

S. No.	Research Guide	Affiliating University	Citations	Rank
1	Balram K Gupta	Panjab University	10	1
2	C Rajashekhar	Karnatak University	07	2
3	B N Sampath	Utkal University	06	3.
4	M L Upadhyaya	University of Calcutta		
5	A S Bhat	University of Kashmir		
6	Naresh Kumar	Maharshi Dayanand University	05	4
7	O V Nandimath	National Law School of India University, Karnataka		
8	Pramod Kumar	Dayalbagh Educational Institute	04	5
9	Devidas G. Maley	Gulbarga University		
10	V N Paranjapee	Symbiosis International University		
11	Jaivir Singh	Jawaharlal Nehru University		

DISCUSSIONS

As per the results observed from this study, a large number of Law PhD theses is not getting citations. This could be due to the quality of the work reported or due to the less visibility of the research reported in form of research journal publications. Further, according to the study there are 1057 universities in India but only 568 universities are contributed in Shodhganga repository whereas 654 universities have signed MoU. This

is a clear indication that some of the universities yet have not contributed in this project. Thus it is suggested that remaining universities should also contribute to Shodhganga. This is two way beneficial to the universities too as increasing visibility of the content is helpful to increase citations and also it helps to attract the new researchers.

CONCLUSION

The state university contribution is significantly higher than that of central, private and other popular deemed universities. There is a regular increase in the Law PhD theses submission to the ETD in Shodhganga but citations are not increasing with that pace.

Uttar Pradesh has contributed in terms of largest number of law PhD theses whereas Kvumpu University is the largest contributor. However, Panjab University holds the credit for maximum number of citations. There is an urgent need to increase the contribution of universities in Shodhganga as a large number of universities are still not contributing in this project. Referring to its positive side, number of submissions has increased gradually and this is a good sign for the future.

References

- 1) Merriam –Webster <https://www.merriam-webster.com/> (Accessed September 2022)
- 2) Echeverria M, Stuart D and Blanke T, Medical Thesis and derivative articles: dissemination of contents and publication patterns, *Scientometrics*, 102 (1) (2015). 559- 586. DOI:10.1007/s11192-014-1442-0
- 3) Juznic P, Grey Literature produced and published by Universities: A Case for ETDs, (2010). Available at https://books.google.co.in/books?hl=en&lr=&id=Wvt_lwB2KIYC&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Grey+Literature+in+Library+and+Information+Studies,+pp.+3951&ots=qz3qVGbt6&sig=uLkWktlz7I3OEqKZb0Dkz-IW14c#v=onepage&q&f=false (Accessed in September 2022).
- 4) Singh R K, Singh A P and Singh A K, Research Trends in Field of Library and Information Science: A Case Study of DLIS Aligarh Muslim University through Shodhganga repository, *Library Progress (International)*, 38 (2) (2018). 158- 165. DOI: 10.5958/2320-317X.2018.00016.8
- 5) Shodhganga, about, available at <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/> (Accessed on September 2022)
- 6) Ankita Saloi (2021) Contribution of Electronic Thesis and Dissertations (ETDs) by the Central Universities of Northeast India to the Shodhganga Project of Inflibnet: An Evaluative Study Library Philosophy and Practice EISSN: 1522-0222
- 7) Ashok Thomas and Prasanth MP (2021) Thomas, Ashok and MP, Prasanth, "Integration of Kerala Academic Library Network (KALNET) and Indian Access Management Federation (INFED) in the Higher Educational Institutions of Kerala: A Conceptual research" (2021). *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 6071. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=11350&context=libphilprac> (Accessed September 2022)
- 8) Srikanth H G (2021) Contribution of Electronic Thesis and Dissertations (ETD) In Legal Research to Shodhganga Repository: An Overview *Journal of Advances in Library and Information Science* EISSN: 2277-2219